

EFFECTIVENESS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SUGGESTIVE SKILLS IN TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF DIFFERENTIAL APPROACH

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Annotation: In this article, there is a classification of pedagogical skills and the socio-pedagogical necessity of their development in teachers, improving the system of training pedagogues today, improving the skills of pedagogues, developing pedagogical skills and abilities. Each pedagogical ability has its own characteristics, and it is explained that it is necessary for a pedagogue to know them and to be able to develop these abilities.

Key words and phrases: sports, folk traditional values, intercultural relations, practical skills, continuous education, individual qualities, economic development, educational standards, education and training, scientific-methodical, subjective innovation in students.

Introduction

In modern science and pedagogical practice, education is the opportunity to transfer the socio-cultural experience of previous generations to the learner in a goal-oriented manner and to organize the assimilation of this experience, as well as the opportunity to apply this experience in different situations. and active action related to readiness is understood. Education, of course, as its condition, offers teaching and learning processes for mastering this experience.

Education implies a goal-oriented influence on the formation of certain values, principles of behavior, evaluation system, attitudes towards oneself, surrounding people, work, and society. Education is considered as a whole effect of the entire educational environment, although for analytical and pedagogical purposes it is divided according to moral, aesthetic, labor, physical and others.

We will consider the process of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers from the point of view of their interrelationship with the pedagogical concepts of "formation", "recovery", "socialization", "education", "development". If socialization is the process of formation of a person in certain social conditions, during which a person has a certain social experience, then education is directed to the goal of forming a person with the help of pedagogical influence in accordance with a certain socio-pedagogical ideal. is a process. Formation means interaction of a person with real reality, physical and socio-psychological changes in the structural structure of a person.

The pedagogical value of development is defined as "aspiring-advanced, quantitative and qualitative, mental somatic and spiritual changes" are understood.

The analysis of the main principles in the development of modern continuous professional education showed that each of them activated the idea of integration. It is the integrity of the educational system that develops the suggestive abilities of the pedagogue, the formation of the personality of a specialist, views on the continuity of education, confirmation of the unity of pedagogical processes of personal education and upbringing, standardization of

education, institutionalized education and independent education. It is reflected in the interdependence of the processes of education. At the same time, there is a desire for differentiation in continuous education, which is semi-functionality of education, independent education, independent study, independent upbringing, recognition of the subjectivity of learners, educational programs and variety of issues, a large number of subjects' points of view, the concept of innovativeness is characteristic, and many pedagogical objects belong to it.

Methods

The analysis of advanced principles in continuing education shows that there is a phenomenon of differentiation, which is important in the training of specialists, this aspect will be taken into account in the future development of a differentiated concept in continuing education of social professionals

Based on the differential approach, the use of modeling for the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers at all stages and the dynamics of changes in pedagogical activity are reflected in all stages of their continuous professional development. At each stage, the components of pedagogical activity are determined (specific types of activities managed on the basis of strategic goals and motives, professional actions directed at tactical goals, ways of performing actions in specific conditions and evaluating their effectiveness, etc.), which is the basis for determining the professional functions of a pedagogue. lib serves (motivational, purposeful and fast) and leads to development.

The organizational and fundamental model of preparation for pedagogical activities in higher education is a single cycle (external and internal) and consists of separate modules: the needs of stakeholders in the training of specialists, the formation of the main goals of the educational program, the integration of education to achieve educational goals and differentiation), determining results, evaluating educational results, determining the level of development of educational programs, organizing the educational process, building a multifunctional educational space, evaluating the quality of education (internal and external), Education results and prospects for further professional training.

The development of suggestive abilities in future teachers is carried out in accordance with the step-by-step formation of each training course.

At the stage of realizing the status of a teacher (the first course), a new social role of a person is observed, as well as a holistic development related to mastering the general scientific foundations of the profession. It is distinguished by the adaptability of the person to the influence of others. During this period, students usually do not distinguish their roles. Students get acquainted with the unique forms of community life. At this stage, students establish new social relationships and adapt to different conditions.

At the suggestive self-awareness stage (second year), the specialized development of students' personality continues, their cultural demands and needs are formed. They gain confidence and independence, are not only included in all forms of education and upbringing, but also actively participate in public organizations. In this period, attention is mainly paid to general professional subjects.

At the stage of suggestive self-determination (the third year), students' attention to specialized academic subjects is strengthened, and their motives for professional activity are strengthened. At this stage, interest in scientific research increases and the characteristics of

the chosen profession are studied. At the same time, the social activity of students develops and the level of self-organization increases.

The suggestive preparation stage (fourth course) is related to the attitude to pedagogical activity and encourages mastering the methods and technologies of the specialist's work. At this stage, the student more consciously approaches the choice of the place of practice to gain pedagogical experience. The characteristics and specific qualities of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers can be expressed as follows:

Results

The main areas of development of suggestive abilities in future teachers are theoretical, practical, research and general cultural areas. The theoretical direction implements all blocks of the educational content that make up the state educational standard, the practical direction is represented by various types of practice - educational practice, industrial practice and internship practice, the research direction is research in the educational system. reveals the organizational basis of its activity. According to him, it can be added to the educational process, additional to it or parallel to it. The general cultural direction is represented by various types of organized activities: cultural and recreational, vocational guidance, civil rights, information awareness, health care. The result of the implementation of all is shown by a professional competitive specialist in the social sphere, their quality is shown in various forms of representation - state attestation, in the form of a portfolio.

The development of suggestive skills in future teachers as an integral system of activities carried out in higher pedagogical education has its own trends, principles, goals, tasks, content, work forms and methods, as well as means of increasing its effectiveness. At the same time, the goals, tasks, content, forms and methods of working on the studied problem should correspond to the general laws of personal development. The coordination, hierarchy and functioning of the listed components in an integral structure presupposes the presence of control elements in any pedagogical system. And this fully applies to the system of preparing a student for pedagogical activity in order to implement a differential approach. This includes the development of theoretical foundations that are compatible with the stable operation of the system under certain conditions.

Suggestive skills in future teachers, that is, the system of preparation for pedagogical activities aimed at working with students should be based on the principles of scientific nature, continuity, systematicity and unity of theoretical and practical training.

The scientific character of the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers is a reflection of modern scientific achievements, advanced pedagogical experiences, new concepts of teaching and upbringing, and, of course, the study of methods of scientific pedagogical research in the structure of psychological and pedagogical sciences. During our research, we were convinced that although the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers is theoretically unique, there are still problems in practical activities. This is due to the fact that the principle of the unity of educational theory and practice is not given priority.

As the main goal of the studied problem, we consider the formation of the knowledge and skills necessary for the implementation of the suggestive abilities development system in future teachers as a promising work. The operation of the system developed by us is subordinated to the process of achieving the goal and choosing optimal ways among possible alternatives. By the result of the educational system, we understand a certain step in the

professional development of the student, which is expressed in the process of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers.

We will consider the composition of the system that ensures the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers. It is known that today's labor market objectively demands a socially and professionally competent, dialectical thinking, in-depth knowledge, cultural and competitive person. In this regard, we believe that the content of developing suggestive skills in future teachers based on a differential approach should include:

- formation of a universal system of knowledge and skills necessary for the implementation of this type of activity;
- organization of elective courses along with mandatory subjects of the basic plan of higher education;
- focus on the priority of research and individual training programs carried out in the joint effective activity of the teacher and student, the individual form of work with the future pedagogue (specialist) focused on the uniqueness of his real educational opportunities and abilities application, development of human abilities and its use, application of experiences of foreign countries in formation of knowledge and skills.

In addition, logical-research, cognitive-research, research-creative tasks are defined within each task group. This classification is aimed at preparing future teachers to creatively solve various problems in the pedagogical process aimed at developing suggestive abilities.

Educational and logical tasks allow students to understand the important features of methodological concepts related to teaching based on a differential approach. By educational and logical tasks, we understand the tasks in which the student understands the logic of traditional schemes of solving professional and pedagogical tasks, analyzes and evaluates their alternative solutions, and chooses a certain set of actions. These types of tasks are characterized by imitation of activities. There is an opportunity to choose the recommended scheme for solving the pedagogical problem (task) without correction. Because logical tasks have a positive effect on mastering the learning material. It is determined that a student with a low level of logical preparation will encounter many problems in the course of his work, will not be able to solve them, and as a result will face a professional crisis.

Educational and logical tasks include methods of finding new knowledge and searching for them in the field of education. These types of tasks play a special role in gathering real material on the problem. If educational and logical tasks are related to reproductive activity, then logical tasks are more descriptive (collection and analysis of materials on the problem, its theoretical understanding, as well as the process of implementation of this activity). So, when we say logical-search problems, as a result of solving them, the student will have the opportunity to solve them based on new knowledge or knowledge and solution methods known to him.

Research tasks. In the process of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers on the basis of a differential approach, this task is a generalized concept that includes both features of a cognitive and problematic task. From this point of view, we understand the tasks of research as unity, in the process of which the student uses the new pedagogical technologies known to him and developed them for the implementation of the activity, and has the opportunity to come to independent conclusions based on theoretical and practical conditions.

Creative tasks. It seems that there is a problematic task to ensure the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers in the implementation of education based on the differential approach. The problem is based on a certain problematic situation, it includes situations related to finding a solution to some dialectical contradictions, being able to offer alternative answers to the studied problem in case of lack of time and information. We include the individual way of thinking, the processing of the content of a creative problem, and the forms of independent research into the specific features of solving creative problems. So, in our opinion, creative tasks form the system of knowledge and skills necessary for the implementation of creative activities of the student.

Discussion (Obsujdenie/Discussion). Proposing evaluation-corrective tasks on the basis of a differential approach is related to the need to form a reflective position in the process of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers, which creates conditions for the formation of this task. Introspection of learning activities includes skills related to self-esteem. These tasks serve to identify and correct errors, to provide a mechanism of interdependence with methods that are effective at all stages of activity implementation.

In preparing future teachers for suggestive pedagogical activity, we took into account the following requirements:

- ☒ it is necessary to popularize the practice of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers, to effectively interpret this work, to combine tasks aimed at constructive-creative levels;

- ☒ the complexity of tasks should gradually increase:

- ☒ the system should create opportunities for the implementation of objective methods of control and self-control.

It is also desirable to determine the criteria for developing suggestive abilities in future teachers.

Constructor method. A method aimed at controlling the student's understanding of the essence of the subject. In this case, the student describes all the constructions that come to his mind (imagination) of the essence of the subject in his work by means of images.

“Constructor” The steps of the method are as follows

Figure 2.4

Understanding stage	Perception stage	Analytical stage	Independent perception stage (perceived topic is presented in the form of a scheme, picture, form)
List the principles of being able to follow through on students based on mental and emotional-volitional	What explains the importance of the principles of mental and emotional-volitional impact on students?	The importance of principles in the education of the ability to influence students mentally and emotionally.	What is the basis for the development of the ability to influence students mentally and emotionally?

influence.			
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Problem methods such as analysis of specific socio-pedagogical situations and the method of social design are used as alternative methods of teaching.

The uniqueness of active learning methods is that they provide the following opportunities in practice:

- involving each student in active knowledge and professionally oriented process, not passive knowledge acquisition, but active personal knowledge, practical application of acquired knowledge and clear understanding of where and for what purposes this knowledge can be used;

- searching, processing and using information in order to form one's own independent but reasonable opinion on a specific spiritual and spiritual problem;

- identifying developing social problems and solving them together.

The development of suggestive skills in future teachers based on a differential approach is aimed at achieving the following goals:

- on the basis of the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers, to have a mental and emotional-volitional influence on students and to create the skills of being able to follow their own footsteps;

- to develop the skills and ability to solve the problems of developing suggestive abilities in future teachers;

- mastering methods of solving pedagogical problems and implementing self-control.

Independent work is a mandatory element of education, taking into account that it is of particular importance in preparing a future teacher for personal growth throughout his life, the totality of independent work tools in this research work is a factor that ensures the quality of education. defined as The independent work of students as a factor of ensuring the quality of education in higher educational institutions is the main reason for revealing the human potential for the formation of the readiness and stable need for personal and professional self-education and self-development of future specialists. and it is necessary to create certain conditions for its implementation.

Conclusion

On the basis of a differential approach, we developed the following groups in the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers, taking into account their interests, opportunities and levels of knowledge acquisition.

In conclusion, as a component of the development of suggestive abilities in future teachers, it is carried out on the basis of interlinking a set of specific tasks of theoretical, methodical and practical with educational-logical, investigative, creative and evaluation-corrective nature. .

References:

1. "Social pedagogy" explanatory dictionary of terms. Namangan.: NamDU publishing house. 2017. -B. 48.
2. Kudratov T. Fundamentals of speech culture. -Tashkent.: Fundamentals of speech culture. 1993. -B. 79.

3. Березуцкая Ю.П. Подготовка организаторов образования к анализу управленческой деятельности на основе системы мотивационного программно-целевого управления: Автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук. – Барнаул, 1999. – 17 с.
4. Майоров А.Н., Сахарчук Л.Б., Сотов А.В. Элементы педагогического мониторинга и региональных стандартов в управлении. – СПб., 1992. – 35 с.
5. Turgunov S.T. Theoretical foundations of the effectiveness of management activities of educational institution leaders // Vocational education. - 2006. - No. 1. - p. 55.
6. Saydullaeva, A. R. (2022). Gender Factors in Raising the Intellectual and Social Status of Women in Universities. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 103-107
7. Shodmonov Q.O. Preparation of vocational education students of higher educational institutions for management activities: Ped.f.n. ... diss. - Tashkent, 2008. - 201 p.